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Influence of Test Anxiety on Students' Interest and Academic Achievement in Chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State: Implications for Counselling.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of test anxiety on students' interest and academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, with implications for counselling. Two research questions guided the study, and two hypotheses were formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey design was adopted, with a population of 5,874 chemistry students from 21 government-owned and grant-aided schools. From this, a sample of 176 students, representing 3% of the population, was selected. Data were collected using a researcher-developed instrument titled Test Anxiety, Students' Interest and Achievement in Chemistry Questionnaire (TASIACQ), which contained 10 items rated on a modified four-point Likert scale. The instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.77. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the Chi-square (X^2) goodness-of-fit test was employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significance level. A benchmark mean of 2.50 was used in interpreting responses. The findings revealed that test anxiety has a significant influence on both students' interest and academic achievement in chemistry. Based on these findings, it was recommended that school counsellors should implement intervention programmes such as relaxation techniques, stress management workshops, and test-taking skills training to help students manage test anxiety, sustain interest, and improve performance in chemistry.

Keywords: Test Anxiety, Interest, Academic Achievement, Counselling, Chemistry, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Academic achievement and interest are two important indicators of students' success in any subject area. In the sciences, and particularly in chemistry, both achievement and interest are crucial, since the subject requires sustained effort, problem-solving, and conceptual understanding for mastery. Unfortunately, several studies have reported that students' performance in chemistry in Nigeria has remained unsatisfactory, with fewer students opting to study the subject at the senior secondary school level and in external examinations such as WAEC, NECO, and JAMB (Okonji & Okonji, 2014). This poor performance is often accompanied by declining interest, which further worsens students' engagement with the subject. The concern over low achievement and waning interest in chemistry has prompted researchers to look beyond teaching strategies to student-related variables that may shape learning outcomes. Among these variables, test anxiety has received increasing attention as a psychological factor that may negatively affect students' attitudes and performance.

In the teaching-learning process, the use of the test is one of the major practices of determining students' academic progress, achievement, knowledge, attitude and skills acquired in the learning. Therefore, for chemistry learners to have been certified to have acquired the needed knowledge, attitude and skills, they must have passed through effective assessment through test. However, factors like test anxiety as aforementioned, can affect the general performance of chemistry students. Test anxiety is usually an unpleasant, emotional, and psychological response that is often associated with a sense of fear and worry. It is a psychological situation in which people experience extreme hardship and poor test/achievement scores. According to Onyeizugbo (2010), test anxiety is a worry feeling, anxiousness, or disquiet that occurs when a learner confronts any type or level of test or examination. Test anxiety manifests both cognitively and physically, with students often reporting intrusive thoughts, a sense of dread, and negative self-evaluation, alongside physiological symptoms such as sweating, increased heart rate, and muscle tension (Putwain, Nicholson, Connors, & Woods, 2020). The anxiety stems from a fear of failure, a perception of inadequacy, or a belief that poor performance in the test will lead to negative consequences. Generally, test anxiety is a widespread issue in education and a major barrier to academic success, especially in subjects like chemistry that are perceived as difficult or demanding (Zeidner & Matthews, 2020).

A study by Oluoch, Aloka, and Odongo (2018) investigated how students' beliefs about test anxiety influence their achievement in chemistry. The findings showed that students who exhibited high levels of anxiety consistently performed worse than their less anxious peers. Cognitive test anxiety, characterized by excessive worry and negative thoughts about one's performance, was found to be a key factor. The researchers highlighted that reducing cognitive test anxiety could improve students' performance in chemistry by allowing them to focus more on problem-solving rather than their anxious thoughts. Similarly, Oguchienti and Opara (2021) developed a specialized Chemistry Test Anxiety Scale (CTAS) to measure anxiety specifically related to chemistry exams. Their research confirmed that students with higher test anxiety scores tend to have lower academic achievement in chemistry. They emphasized that anxiety in chemistry exams can cause students to underperform, despite having a good understanding of the subject matter and high interest in it.

Students' interest in academic subjects, including chemistry, is a critical factor influencing their engagement, motivation, and overall academic performance. Interest can be defined as a psychological state of being engaged or wanting to learn more about a subject, which often leads to sustained attention and effort. In educational psychology, interest is viewed as both a motivator and a cognitive resource that enhances the learning experience (Hidi & Renninger, 2020). It plays a central role in guiding students' focus, which shapes their learning behaviours, and ultimately influencing how deeply they understand and retain information. Research consistently shows that students who have a high level of interest in a subject are more likely to engage deeply with the content, seek out additional resources, and persist through challenges, all of which are essential behaviours for success in academic disciplines such as chemistry (Linnenbrink-Garcia, Durik, Conley, Barron, Tauer, Karabenick, & Harackiewicz, 2018). Chemistry involves learning about molecular structures, chemical reactions, and abstract concepts that

can be difficult to visualize and understand, especially for students who may not initially see its relevance to their everyday lives. This perception of chemistry as difficult can negatively affect students' attitudes toward the subject, leading to disinterest, disengagement, and lower academic performance.

Academic achievement refers to the measurable outcomes of learning, often reflected in students' test scores, grades, and overall performance in school subjects. It serves as an important indicator of how well educational objectives are being attained. The West African Examinations Council (WAEC) results for 2021 show that fewer than 45% of students obtained credit-level passes in chemistry (WAEC, 2021). This underperformance is often attributed to psychological barriers like test anxiety, which interferes with students' ability to concentrate and recall information during exams (Olatunji & Ogunbode, 2020). Test anxiety, prevalent among students in high-stakes environments, has been shown to correlate with lower performance in challenging subjects like chemistry, where high cognitive demands exacerbate stress (Eze, Opara, & Olamide, 2019).

From the foregoing, it is clear that academic performance and interest in chemistry remain critical challenges in Nigerian secondary schools. Despite the importance of chemistry for national development and students' career prospects, performance in external examinations has remained poor, while interest in the subject continues to decline. Researchers have shifted focus from teaching strategies to student-related variables, identifying test anxiety as a major psychological factor that may hinder both achievement and interest. Test anxiety can reduce students' motivation, weaken their concentration, and impair recall during examinations, thereby limiting their success in chemistry. This situation calls for more attention not only from teachers and curriculum planners but also from school counsellors who can provide interventions to help students overcome test anxiety. It is against this background that the present study investigates the influence of test anxiety on students' interest and academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the vital role chemistry plays in scientific and technological advancement, students' academic performance in the subject has remained consistently low in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. This persistent underachievement has raised concerns among parents, teachers, and policymakers. While several explanations have been suggested, psychological factors such as test anxiety and students' interest in the subject have emerged as critical determinants that deserve closer attention. Although previous studies have examined instructional methods and other factors affecting performance, the combined influence of test anxiety on both students' interest and academic achievement in chemistry has not been adequately explored in the context of secondary schools in Makurdi. This gap makes it difficult to design effective interventions to address the problem. Furthermore, the counselling implications of these psychological factors are often overlooked, even though school counsellors are strategically positioned to help students manage anxiety, sustain interest, and improve academic outcomes. It is against this background that the present study investigates the influence of test anxiety on students' interest and academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, with particular emphasis on its implications for counselling practice.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of test anxiety on students' interest and academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Investigate the influence of test anxiety on students' interest in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.
2. Examine the influence of test anxiety on students' academic performance in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of test anxiety on students' interest in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?

2. What is the influence of test anxiety on students' academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Test anxiety has no significant influence on students' interest in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.
2. Test anxiety has no significant influence on students' academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population comprised 5,874 Chemistry students from 21 government-owned and grant-aided schools, while a sample of 176 students (96 males and 80 females) representing 3% of the population, was selected. Data were collected using a researcher-developed instrument titled Test Anxiety, Students' Interest and Achievement in Chemistry Questionnaire (TASIACQ). The instrument contained 10 items rated on a modified four-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), with scores of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The instrument yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.77 To answer the research questions, descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used, while the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X²) goodness-of-fit test at a 0.05 significance level. A benchmark mean of 2.50 was used for interpreting responses, with scores below 2.50 indicating negative or disagree responses.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Research Question 1: *What is the influence of test anxiety on students' interest in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?*

Table 1: Means Scores of Influence of Test Anxiety on Students' Interest in Chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	I often lose interest in chemistry because I become nervous when tests are approaching.	31	100	20	25	2.78	.902	Agreed
2	My anxiety about chemistry tests makes me less motivated to study the subject.	72	79	9	16	3.18	.893	Agreed
3	Worrying about poor test results reduces my enthusiasm for learning chemistry.	45	104	17	10	3.05	.762	Agreed
4	Fear of failure during chemistry tests makes me dislike the subject.	34	106	20	16	2.90	.815	Agreed
5	My interest in chemistry increases when I am less anxious about tests.	36	95	25	20	2.84	.882	Agreed
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation \bar{X}= 2.95 SD= .850								Agreed

Table 1 shows the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 2.95 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that respondents agreed that test anxiety has influence on students' interest in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Research Question 2: *What is the influence of test anxiety on students' academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State?*

Table 2: Means Scores of Influence of Test Anxiety on Students' Academic Achievement in Chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	Test anxiety makes it difficult for me to recall what I have studied during chemistry exams.	141	25	10	0	3.74	.553	Agreed
7	I usually perform below my ability in chemistry tests because of nervousness.	46	104	16	10	3.06	.761	Agreed
8	Anxiety during tests affects the accuracy of my answers in chemistry.	38	71	36	31	2.66	1.007	Agreed
9	I tend to forget key concepts in chemistry whenever I feel anxious in an examination hall.	36	120	16	4	3.07	.620	Agreed
10	My test scores in chemistry would improve if I did not experience anxiety.	41	96	19	20	2.90	.889	Agreed
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		$\bar{X} = 3.09$		SD = .766		Agreed		

Table 2 shows the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.09 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that respondents agreed that test anxiety has influence on students' academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Hypothesis 1

Test anxiety has no significant influence on students' interest in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Table 3: Chi-square Test of Influence of Test Anxiety on Students' Interest in Chemistry.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	96.409	.000	Sig.
SA	31	44					
A	100	44					
D	20	44					
SD	25	44					
Total	176						

Table 3 revealed that $\chi^2 = 96.409$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that test anxiety has no significant influence on students' interest in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State is therefore, rejected. This implies that test anxiety has significant influence on students' interest in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Hypothesis 2

Test anxiety has no significant influence on students' achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

Table 4: Chi-square Test of Influence of Test Anxiety on Students' Achievement in Chemistry.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	126.00	.000	Sig.
SA	46	44					
A	104	44					
D	16	44					
SD	10	44					
Total	176						

Table 4 revealed that $\chi^2 = 126.000$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p -value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that test anxiety has no significant influence on students' achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State is therefore, rejected. This implies that test anxiety has significant influence on students' achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of findings is arranged around the research questions and hypotheses.

The first finding of this study revealed that test anxiety has a significant influence on students' interest in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. This outcome suggests that when students experience high levels of anxiety before or during chemistry tests, their motivation and enthusiasm for learning the subject tend to decline. Test anxiety can make students perceive chemistry as a stressful subject rather than an exciting one, thereby dampening their interest. This finding is in line with Zeidner (2014), who argued that test anxiety interferes with students' affective disposition toward a subject, often leading to avoidance behaviour and reduced curiosity. Similarly, Putwain and Daly (2014) noted that heightened anxiety about examinations discourages students from engaging actively in the learning process, which in turn reduces their interest in the subject. In science subjects like chemistry, where conceptual understanding requires consistent effort and motivation, test anxiety can therefore serve as a barrier to sustaining students' interest. The implication is that teachers and school counsellors need to provide strategies for anxiety management in order to help students retain a positive orientation toward chemistry.

The second finding revealed that test anxiety also has a significant influence on students' academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. This implies that students' performance in chemistry tests and examinations is directly affected by the levels of anxiety they experience. Excessive worry and nervousness can interfere with cognitive processes such as concentration, memory recall, and problem-solving, which are crucial for academic success in chemistry. This finding aligns with the report of Von der Embse, Jester, Roy, and Post (2018), who observed that students with higher test anxiety generally score lower on standardized assessments compared to their less anxious peers. Effiong and Okoh (2020) highlighted that anxiety significantly hinders secondary school students' ability to perform optimally in science subjects. This suggests that in Makurdi, many students' poor performance in chemistry may not only be due to lack of ability or preparation, but also the disruptive effects of test anxiety on their academic functioning. The implication is that schools should integrate anxiety-reduction strategies such as relaxation techniques, test-taking skills, and counselling support to enhance both students' performance and overall well-being.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that test anxiety has a significant influence on both students' interest and academic achievement in chemistry in Makurdi Local Government Area. Anxiety not only reduces students' motivation and enthusiasm for the subject but also interferes with their performance in tests and examinations. This shows that test anxiety is both an emotional and academic challenge that must be addressed if students are to excel in chemistry. Based on these, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers and school authorities should adopt teaching methods and assessment practices that reduce anxiety, such as interactive lessons, continuous assessments, and supportive feedback, in order to sustain students' interest in chemistry.
2. School counsellors should implement intervention programmes, including relaxation techniques, stress management workshops, and test-taking skill training, to help students manage anxiety and improve their academic achievement.

Counselling Implications

The findings of this study have important implications for counselling practice in secondary schools, particularly in addressing the emotional and academic challenges posed by test anxiety among students.

1. Counsellors can design individual and group counselling sessions that help students identify, understand, and manage the symptoms of test anxiety, thereby reducing fear and worry associated with chemistry tests.
2. Through academic counselling, students can be guided on effective study habits, time management, and test-taking strategies that will minimize anxiety and improve their achievement in chemistry.
3. Counsellors can implement motivation-enhancing programmes such as career talks, mentorship, and workshops that link chemistry learning to real-life applications, thereby rebuilding students' interest and positive attitude toward the subject.

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